

A wearable stereo vision-based obstacle detection system for visually impaired individuals

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Abstract. Blind and visually impaired individuals face daily challenges in navigating autonomously in unfamiliar urban or domestic environments. Navigation poses critical challenges as obstacles and dangerous objects can compromise their safety and autonomy. Assistive technologies for visually impaired users have evolved to facilitate interaction with a complex and dynamic world, offering increasingly promising solutions. This work presents a wearable computer vision system implemented on a Raspberry Pi 4, utilizing an Intel RealSense D415 camera, capable of detecting and classifying objects and obstacles while estimating and verbally indicating their distance in real time, thus enhancing user autonomy and safety.

Keywords: Computer Vision · Assistive Technology · Object Detection.

1 Introduction

In everyday life, human eyes are the primary means of acquiring information from the surrounding environment. According to the World Health Organization, 285 million people worldwide have visual impairments, including 39 million who are blind [14]. Blind and visually impaired individuals, therefore, face daily challenges in navigating autonomously in complex environments, such as urban or domestic settings. Traditionally, blind individuals rely on white canes or guide dogs for navigation. White canes help detect obstacles, while guide dogs assist the user in reaching their destination. However, both solutions provide limited environmental details, making navigation in complex environments a significant challenge. Indeed, tasks such as crossing streets, moving through crowds, and recognizing objects in unfamiliar places can be risky due to the inability to perceive depth, motion, and spatial relationships. These challenges affect personal safety, independence, and overall quality of life, emphasizing the need for more advanced assistive technologies.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision (CV) offer promising solutions by enabling real-time interpretation of the environment. By combining image processing algorithms with AI models, CV can accurately detect, recognize, and classify objects. These technologies have applications across various

Fig. 1: Hardware architecture layout of the proposed system.

fields, such as healthcare [16], automotive [13] and industrial automation [8], enhancing accessibility and increasing efficiency. In robotics, CV plays a crucial role in enabling robots to perceive and understand their surroundings, leading to advancements in tasks like autonomous navigation, object recognition, and robotic assistance [5]. By integrating CV, robots become more intuitive, responsive, and capable of executing complex tasks with enhanced precision. For example, in [15], the authors proposed an architecture for user identification and social navigation in mobile robotics. Their approach leverages CV algorithms for gesture and facial recognition to identify users and facilitate navigation in social contexts. Similarly, in [18], a YOLO-based model was introduced to enhance object detection for service robots, improving their efficiency in navigating indoor environments. Beyond navigation, CV is also useful in improving robotic manipulation and motion planning. In [6], the authors proposed a layered architecture that incorporates visual foundation models to enhance task execution. Moreover, CV technologies can be integrated in human-robot collaboration, as demonstrated in [2], where the *AFFDEX 2.0* module was employed to monitor real-time facial expressions during such interactions.

In the context of accessibility, CV offers a significant opportunity for the development of assistive systems for blind and visually impaired individuals, allowing the detection and classification of obstacles in their environment. Current solutions implement diverse approaches to enhance spatial perception. AIris [4] integrates high-resolution cameras and natural language processing (NLP) to provide real-time audio scene descriptions, achieving great performance in object recognition and text reading. SOMAVIP [11] employs depth cameras and IoT frameworks to deliver semantic feedback in urban environments. RealSense-based systems [21], using stereo depth sensors such as R200 and RS410, enable efficient obstacle detection and path generation. YOLO-based systems [7] focus

on light RGB object detection, ensuring high speed at the cost of depth accuracy, while simpler configurations with ultrasonic sensors [17] prioritize cost efficiency.

Despite these innovations, assistive technologies still face persistent challenges. Many solutions rely on centralized processing or cloud infrastructures, introducing latency and limiting usability in offline environments or areas with poor connectivity. Others provide minimal or non-semantic feedback, reducing the user’s ability to gain a detailed awareness of their surroundings. Another challenge is the integration of machine learning models into embedded systems due to the inherent limitations of these devices. Therefore, achieving a balance between advanced functionality, portability, cost efficiency, and adaptability to dynamic and unstructured scenarios remains an open challenge.

In this work, we propose a wearable computer vision system, schematized in Fig. 1, capable of detecting and classifying objects and obstacles while estimating and verbally indicating their distance in real time, thus enhancing users’ autonomous mobility and safety. Specifically, the system employs a lightweight object detection model, *EfficientDet-Lite0*, in conjunction with the Intel RealSense D415 RGB-D sensor, which utilizes stereo vision technology. The system processes RGB and depth data in parallel on a Raspberry Pi 4, delivering real-time semantic feedback without relying on cloud infrastructure. In addition, portability and affordability enhance the system’s usability for real-world deployment. By addressing challenges related to depth accuracy, real-time feedback, and user-friendly experience, this work contributes to the development of scalable, reliable, and accessible assistive technologies for individuals with visual impairments.

2 Hardware and software components

This section introduces the components used in the development of the proposed system. The hardware consists of the Intel RealSense D415 depth camera and the Raspberry Pi 4 single-board computer, which together provide real-time depth perception and computational capabilities.

The Intel RealSense D415 camera, shown in Fig. 1, is an advanced depth-sensing device designed for precise 3D perception. It employs an active stereo vision system that integrates two infrared sensors with an infrared projector, enabling the generation of high-resolution depth maps in real time. Its RGB sensor further allows the acquisition of color images synchronized with depth data, making it highly suitable for object recognition and 3D modeling applications. Complementing the camera, the Raspberry Pi 4, also depicted in Fig. 1, is a powerful single-board computer designed for embedded applications, featuring a compact size and a flexible design. It is well-suited for projects that require a balance between functionality and low power consumption.

The following sections will delve into the software methodologies implemented in the system, including stereo vision techniques for depth estimation and the *EfficientDet-Lite0* algorithm for object detection and classification.

2.1 Stereo vision

Stereo vision is the process of estimating the depth of scene points based on their positional variation between two image sensors placed at a known relative distance.

In this work, stereo vision is employed to acquire depth data, which is then used for obstacle detection. This process relies on identifying correspondences between elements (objects or recognizable details) present in the input images. When an object appears in both images, its position differs slightly between the two; this difference, known as disparity, is used to compute the object’s distance from the observation point. By iterating this operation for all identifiable points in both images, a disparity map is generated [12].

Specifically, the stereo vision process consists of four main stages: i) *Offline calibration*: to obtain the intrinsic parameters of the two cameras (such as focal length, image center, and lens distortion parameters) and the extrinsic parameters (i.e., the relative position of the two cameras, referred to as the baseline, and their relative rotation); ii) *Rectification*: which removes lens distortions and reduces the correspondence search from a two-dimensional to a one-dimensional operation, thus accelerating disparity computation; iii) *Stereo matching*: which aims at identifying homologous points in the stereo image pair; iv) *Triangulation*: given the disparity map, baseline, and focal length, triangulation determines the 3D position of the corresponding points in space.

2.2 Object detection

Object detection is a fundamental task that involves identifying instances of objects within an image and classifying them into predefined categories. Numerous high-speed algorithms have been developed for object detection. Currently, object detection models can be divided into two main categories [22]: two-stage and one-stage detectors. The first consists of models that break down the task into multiple stages, following a *coarse-to-fine* approach. In contrast, the latter comprises models designed to complete the detection process in a single step using a single neural network.

In this work, to ensure the real-time performance of the proposed system on a single-board computer, we adopt the *EfficientDet-Lite0* model [20]. *EfficientDet-Lite0* is a lightweight and optimized one-stage detector model designed for devices with limited resources and belongs to the EfficientDet family, which uses the EfficientNet convolutional neural network (CNN) as its backbone [19].

3 Proposed architecture

As introduced above, this work proposes a CV system equipped with an object detection model and stereo vision technology for depth estimation. The intended application scenario is assistive technology for visually impaired or blind individuals, providing them with audio feedback on obstacles in their surroundings.

Fig. 2: General overview of the image processing stages involved in the system, which consists of two main processing pipelines: the obstacle detection process (green), and the object detection process (blue).

The objective is to integrate these functionalities into a wearable platform and to leverage the combined information to detect and classify objects and obstacles in real time. Specifically, in the context of this work, the term *object* refers to an identified element in the scene that could potentially become an obstacle. In contrast, the term *obstacle* refers to any surface within the captured scene that, even if not associated with a specific object, poses a risk because its proximity falls below a critical distance threshold relative to the user.

3.1 System overview

The system was developed within a Python 3.7 virtual environment, utilizing key libraries such as NumPy [9], OpenCV [3], multiprocessing, TensorFlow [1], and PyRealSense2 [10], the latter being necessary for camera integration.

As schematized in Fig. 2, the system consists of two main processing pipelines that form its core:

- **Obstacle detection process:** by processing depth maps collected by the RGBD stereo camera, the system identifies areas in the scene that are at a critical distance, defined as below a certain threshold;
- **Object classification process:** utilizing the *EfficientDet-Lite0* model, the system detects objects in RGB frames and associates their position with that of the obstacles to provide a combined visualization and communication.

The detailed execution flow of the proposed architecture is illustrated in Fig. 3. Specifically, the process begins with a *main* execution thread, which launches three parallel processes to handle data acquisition from the camera, obstacle detection, and object detection, respectively.

3.2 Stream reader process

Given the computational demands of object detection and obstacle detection, which represent the primary bottlenecks in the pipeline, a multiprocessing-based approach was implemented. This design choice, preferred over multithreading, enables parallel execution of independent processes, optimizing performance, particularly in embedded environments. The *stream reader process*, shown in yellow in Fig. 3, corresponds to Algorithm 1, which is highlighted in red within the yellow block. This process is responsible for acquiring depth and RGB frames from the RealSense camera. Specifically, it initializes a pipeline to capture frames, processes the incoming data, and inserts the frames into two separate queues: the *Depth queue* for depth data and the *RGB queue* for RGB data. The process runs continuously until a *stopEvent* is triggered, as detailed in Algorithm 1.

3.3 Obstacle detection process

The *obstacle detection process*, shown in green in Fig. 3, is responsible for real-time depth data processing and acts as a consumer of the *Depth queue*. It retrieves frames from the queue and applies *pre-processing and contour extraction*, followed by *obstacle contours sorting and filtering*. Through these operations, the process identifies a set of detected obstacles computing their corresponding distances.

Pre-processing and contour extraction Given an RGB frame (Fig. 4a), a corresponding depth map can be derived, as illustrated in Fig. 4b. Considering a depth map as a two-dimensional matrix of numerical values representing the distance of projected points from the observation point, the *pre-processing and contour extraction process* aims to identify, sort, and filter the contours of obstacles in an image. As outlined in Algorithm 2, highlighted in red in Fig. 3 within the green block, the process begins with the generation of a binary mask by applying a depth threshold between 400 *mm* and 2500 *mm* (Fig. 4c). The lower bound corresponds to the camera’s minimum detection range, while the upper bound is empirically determined to define the region where obstacles are considered potentially dangerous. Next, morphological operations are applied to the mask to reduce noise and enhance image quality. Finally, contour detection is performed, and only the n most significant obstacles (i.e., those with the largest contours) are retained. An example result is shown in Fig. 4d, where the extracted contour is highlighted in green.

Fig. 3: Architecture execution flow diagram consisting of three parallel processes for handling data acquisition from the camera (yellow), obstacle detection (green), and object detection (blue).

Fig. 4: Output of the different stages of the *obstacle detection process* in an outdoor environment: (a) an RGB frame capturing a car; (b) the corresponding depth map; (c) the generated binary mask; and (d) the output of Algorithm 2 and Algorithm 3, where the detected contour is shown in green and the centroid in purple.

Centroid computation After detecting obstacles, their centroids are computed using image moments to estimate their geometric centers. These centroids are then stored for tracking purposes.

In particular, to ensure temporal consistency across frames, newly detected centroids are compared with previously identified obstacles following the procedure outlined in Algorithm 3, highlighted in red in Fig. 3 within the green block. The comparison is based on the following criteria:

- *Proximity matching*: obstacles detected within a threshold of 50 pixels across consecutive frames are considered the same object, and their attributes (e.g., position and distance) are updated accordingly;
- *Merging overlapping detections*: if a newly detected centroid falls within an extended radius proportional to an existing obstacle’s area, it is merged with that obstacle. Otherwise, it is registered as a new obstacle;
- *Filtering transient detections*: only obstacles corresponding to newly detected centroids are retained, while transient or noise-induced detections are discarded.

Specifically, the distance of each obstacle is calculated using the *compute_distance* method of the *Obstacle* class, as described in Algorithm 4. This method identifies the closest point within the obstacle and stores the minimum distance as an internal attribute when the obstacle is created or updated.

Algorithm 1: Stream reader process

Require: Depth queue, RGB queue, stopEvent
Ensure: Frames inserted into the queues

```

1 begin
2   pipeline ← New pipeline;
3   config ← New configuration;
4   pipelineWrapper ← PipelineWrapper(pipeline);
5   Start(pipeline, config);
6   while ¬ IsSet(stopEvent) do
7     frames ← WaitForFrames(pipeline);
8     depthFrame, colorFrame ← GetFrames(frames);
9     if depthFrame = NULL or colorFrame = NULL then
10      | continue;
11     depthImage ← AsArray(GetData(depthFrame));
12     colorImage ← AsArray(GetData(colorFrame));
13     if IsFull(Depth queue) then
14      | Get(Depth queue);
15     Put(Depth queue, depthImage);
16     if IsFull(RGB queue) then
17      | Get(RGB queue);
18     Put(RGB queue, colorImage);
19   Stop(pipeline);

```

Furthermore, based on the centroid’s position, each obstacle is assigned a label indicating its approximate location within the frame. The frame is divided into six regions, defined by the combination of two vertical sections (*top* and *bottom*) and three horizontal sections (*left*, *center*, and *right*). An example is shown in Fig. 4d, where the computed centroid is highlighted in purple.

This *centroid computation* approach enhances robustness by ensuring that only persistent obstacles are tracked over time, reducing the impact of spurious detections.

Algorithm 2: Pre-processing and contour extraction process

Require: Image frame, n
Ensure: n sorted and filtered contours by ContourArea

```

1 begin
2   maskObstacle ← InRange(frame, 400, 2000);
3   closedMask ← MorphologyEx(maskObstacle, MORPHCLOSE, (7, 7));
4   contours ← FindContours(closedMask, ...);
5   sortedContours ← Sort(contours, key ← ContourArea, reverse);
6   filteredContours ← sortedContours[:n];
7   return filteredContours;

```

Algorithm 3: Update and create new obstacles

Require: List of previous obstacles: previousObstacles, detected center: detectedCenter, frame, contours extracted form the frame
Ensure: Updated list of obstacles: obstacles

```

1 begin
2   found ← False;
3   for o ∈ previousObstacles do
4     if o.isNear(detectedCenter, 50) then
5       o.distance ← o.calculateDistance(frame, contour);
6       o.center ← detectedCenter;
7       found ← True;
8       break;
9     if o.isNear(detectedCenter, o.radius) then
10      o.area ← o.area + ContourArea(contour);
11      o.updateRadius();
12      o.distance ← o.calculateDistance(frame, contour);
13      found ← True;
14      break;
15 if Not found then
16   obstacles.Append(new Obstacle(ContourArea(contour),
    detectedCenter, frame, contour, useMinDistance=True));

```

Algorithm 4: Compute Distance from Depth Frame

Require: Depth frame depthFrame, contour contour
Ensure: Minimum valid distance or None

```

1 begin
2   mask ← ZerosLike(depthFrame, uint8);
3   DrawContours(mask, [contour], -1, 255, FILLED);
4   distances ← depthFrame[mask == 255];
5   validDistances ← distances[distances > 0];
6   if length(validDistances) > 0 then
7     return GetMin(validDistances);
8   else
9     return None;

```

3.4 Object detection and pairing process

The *object detection and pairing process*, shown in blue in Fig. 3, analyzes RGB frames to identify and classify relevant objects within a given context, such as cars, people, tables, or chairs. Subsequently, the process will be responsible for providing an audible verbal feedback to indicate the presence of the most dangerous obstacle for the user. In the proposed system, this process consists of four key steps:

Model configuration The object detection model is set up with the following key parameters: i) *Number of threads*: optimized experimentally and set to 4 for efficient execution; ii) *Maximum objects per frame*: limited to 3 to ensure focused detection; iii) *Confidence threshold*: a minimum confidence score required for an object to be included in the results.

Frame pre-processing and object detection Before the RGB frame is processed by the model, the pre-processing steps described in Algorithm 5 are performed.

The pre-processing includes horizontal flipping to achieve a selfie-view, color space conversion from BGR to RGB, and resizing to dimensions suitable for the object detection model. Finally, the preprocessed image is converted into a tensor representation and passed to the object detector to obtain detection results. The output is a structured data object containing a list of detected classes within the frame, along with the dimensions and positions of the corresponding bounding boxes, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Output of the *image pre-processing and object detection algorithm* in indoor environment.

Algorithm 5: Image pre-processing and object detection

Require: color image from RGB Queue: colorImage, object detector: detector
Ensure: Detection result: detectionResult

```

1 begin
2   image ← Flip(colorImage);
3   rgbImage ← ConvertColor(image, BGR2RGB);
4   resizedRgbImage ← Resize(rgbImage, (640, 480));
5   inputTensor ← CreateFromArray(resizedRgbImage);
6   detectionResult ← Detect(detector, inputTensor);
7   return detectionResult

```

Distance estimation and pairing The final step in the *object detection and pairing process* associates detected objects with obstacles and determines their respective distances from the user. This step takes as input the list of obstacles received through the *Obstacle queue*, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Next, the association between detected objects and obstacles is determined using the procedure described in Algorithm 6. Specifically, an object is considered a match with an obstacle if their centers are within 100 pixels of each other. If a match is found, the object’s bounding box, class, and distance are announced verbally and optionally displayed on the screen, as shown in Fig. 6. If no match is found, only the presence of the obstacle and its estimated distance are communicated.

This real-time pairing of detected objects with obstacle distances enhances spatial awareness, ensuring accurate and meaningful feedback for the user.

Fig. 6: Output of the *detected objects and obstacle matching* algorithm in outdoor environment.

Algorithm 6: Detected objects and obstacle matching

Require: List of obstacles: *obstaclesList*, object center: *center*, frame
Ensure: Frame with distance information

```

1 begin
2   matched  $\leftarrow$  False;
3   for obstacle  $\in$  obstaclesList do
4     distance  $\leftarrow$  GetDistance(obstacle);
5     if distance  $\neq$  None and obstacle.isNear(center, 100)
6       DisplayBoundingBoxAndInfo(frame, obstacle);
7       AnnounceObjectInfo(obstacle);
8       matched  $\leftarrow$  True;
9       break;
9   if not matched AnnounceObstaclePresence(distance);
```

Verbal output feedback Lastly, once the most dangerous obstacle for the user has been detected, the proposed system provides verbal acoustic feedback to signal its presence, as illustrated by the gray block within the blue block in Fig. 3. Specifically, the system announces the obstacle’s position, corresponding to the centroid’s label, along with its distance from the user. If the detected obstacle is a classified object, the system also specifies its category. Examples of output phrases are: “*Car, bottom-left, 2.56 meters*” or “*Obstacle, bottom-right, 1.2 meters*”.

To avoid excessive audio messages that could be distracting in dynamic environments, obstacle notifications are issued at fixed, configurable intervals t rather than immediately after each detection. This approach filters out transient obstacles while ensuring timely alerts, as t is chosen to remain within safety limits given by the system’s maximum obstacle detection time of 0.4498 s (Tab. 1).

4 Experimental validation

To experimentally validate the proposed architecture (Fig. 1), we conducted a performance test to evaluate the system’s obstacle and object detection times, demonstrating that its performance meets the required specifications. This was followed by a pilot user study with subjects without visual impairments to assess the overall feasibility of the proposed system.

Performance test the system was tested for five consecutive minutes in an indoor environment, during which it detected various obstacles and objects. During execution, the processing times for each obstacle and object detection cycle were recorded in a log file and expressed in seconds. In total, data were collected from 844 cycles in which at least one obstacle was detected and 52 cycles in which at least one object was detected, yielding the results presented in Tab. 1.

From Table 1, the ratio of the average object detection time to the average obstacle detection time indicates that obstacle detection is, on average, approx-

Statistics	Obstacle Detection [s]	Object Detection [s]
Mean	0.1363	2.4574
Variance	0.0024	0.6317
Standard deviation	0.0488	0.7948
Minimum	0.0495	0.5549
Maximum	0.4498	3.6320

Table 1: Performance of the system for obstacle and object detection.

imately 18 times faster than object detection, achieving an execution rate of approximately 7 frames per second.

Considering the performance test results, the system meets the required specifications if the arbitrary audio feedback interval t is at least equal to the maximum obstacle detection time. In this case, the system ensures that obstacles are detected and reported in a timely manner. For instance, if $t = 10$ s, the user receives auditory feedback every 10 s, and the values in Table 1 confirm that, even in the worst case, obstacles can be reported within a maximum delay of approximately 0.45 s. On the other hand, object detection, which includes classification, can take up to 3.63 s, but this remains within an acceptable range depending on the application’s requirements.

Pilot user study The study was conducted in a domestic environment filled with various objects. During testing, the camera was attached to the shirt worn by the user. The study showed that the system is suitable for real-world scenarios. Moreover, participants emphasized the need for improvements in the auditory cues provided by the system and suggested integrating haptic feedback via a smartphone to enhance user experience. Additionally, the user study revealed the need for stably attaching the camera to the shirt to prevent movement-related issues, which could cause errors and delays in obstacle detection. Ensuring a secure attachment would improve both the accuracy and reliability of the system, making it more effective in dynamic environments.

5 Conclusion

We proposed a wearable computer vision system on a Raspberry Pi 4, using an Intel RealSense D415 camera. The system can detect and classify objects and obstacles while estimating and verbally announcing their distance in real time. We evaluated the system through a performance test, confirming that it meets the required specifications, and conducted a pilot user study to assess its overall feasibility. In the future, we plan to enhance the system’s verbal communication by integrating a large language model to generate human-like audio feedback. Additionally, user experience will be improved by conveniently integrating haptic feedback.

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